

THE NEW INNOVATIVE METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH FOR CHILDREN BEING TREATED AT THE CENTER OF CHILDREN'S HEMATOLOGY, ONCOLOGY AND CLINICAL IMMUNOLOGY

Nabieva G.G.

English teacher at State educational institution, "Mehrlı Maktab" under the Ministry of Pre-school and School Education

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13169493>

Abstract. *Hospital Pedagogy comes against a professional reality in which we act and experience daily. Faced with this reality where children are hospitalized, as a pedagogy student, we perceive the possibilities for the pedagogue to act in a space where children and adolescents are often forgotten as children, adolescents and students, ignoring everything they left outside from the hospital seeing only the clinical part of the treatment.*

Keywords: *affordable education, hematology, oncology, clinical immunology, long-term treatment.*

The goal of the "Mehrlı maktab" project is to promote the realization of the child's guaranteed right to receive a quality and affordable education in conditions of long-term treatment and the inability to attend a regular school or kindergarten.

According to the Resolution of Cabinet Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 134 dated On March 29, 2023 about "On measures to further expand the education and training system for children undergoing hematology, oncology, clinical immunology, other inpatient and long-term outpatient treatment" branches of "Mehrlı Maktab" will be established gradually in 2023-2028[1].

"The main goal of the branches is to ensure the social adaptation of children undergoing treatment, their readiness to continue their education in preschool and general secondary education organizations," the decision claims.

Families who have faced a serious and long-term illness of a child experience constant fear for their future and life. This changes their daily routine - for a long time the child finds himself isolated from the usual social environment: kindergarten, school, educational clubs. The main goal of the school is to facilitate a full life of the child during the period of fighting the disease, his recovery and socialization, successful return to his native schools by means of education and medical and social rehabilitation.

"Mehrlı Maktab" state educational institution was established by the decision of the Government. The school has the status of a legal entity and is organized under the Ministry of Public Education.

The school Mehrlı Maktab employs specially trained teaching staff – tutors. A tutor is a teacher who has not only the basic subject qualification of a teacher, educator or teacher of additional education, but also an additional qualification in tutoring a child undergoing long-term treatment. The special competence of a hospital school tutor includes the skills of communicating with a sick child and his parents, as well as the use of strategies for interacting with medical workers. Over the years of successful work of the Mehrlı Maktab, the attention of the state and

society to the teacher working with children undergoing long-term treatment has significantly increased.

The school implements general educational programs for basic and additional education of children undergoing treatment in a medical hospital. A variety of activities motivate children to study, help them adapt to a long stay in a children's hospital and lift their spirits. Training is carried out both in person and remotely. When teaching long-term ill children, special educational technologies of group and individual classes are used. For each child, based on the recommendations of doctors and the state of health, psycho-emotional characteristics and capabilities, an individual educational program is formed.

The following preschool groups can operate in a special school:

pre-school educational hospital groups - groups organized in treatment-prophylactic institutions for children aged 2 to 7 years who are undergoing inpatient treatment and cannot go to pre-school educational institutions due to health reasons;

play groups for children of early developmental age - groups organized in inpatient treatment and prevention institutions for children aged 1.5 to 2 years. Their care and supervision are organized with the active participation of parents;

pre-school educational hospital groups, play groups for children of early developmental age.

Admission of patients to pre-school hospital groups is carried out on the basis of the lists provided by "Mehrli Maktab".

General secondary education in grades 1-11 is provided based on a specially developed curriculum for those treated at the center. The duration of the lesson is 35 minutes in grades 1-4 of primary education (school), and 40 minutes in grades 5-11.

In this case, it is determined that one day of classes should not exceed 3 hours in grades 1-4, and 4 hours in grades 5-11. The duration of the academic week is 5 days.

Hospital pedagogy, as a currently actively developing area of pedagogical science, aims to adapt methods for implementing educational activities in order to ensure pedagogical rehabilitation of a sick child. Hospital pedagogy develops and creates its own content: pedagogical goals, diagnostic tools, patterns, principles of development and formation of the educational environment.

Hospital Pedagogy is an area of pedagogy that is dedicated to the education and care of children and adolescents who, for medical reasons, are unable to attend regular school [2]. This field of study recognizes the importance of learning and cognitive development to the well-being and recovery of young patients.

Hospital Pedagogy is based on a set of principles and practices that aim to guarantee the right to education for all students, regardless of their health condition. Education is seen as a fundamental human right and an important means of promoting social inclusion and equality.

Hospital educators work closely with physicians, nurses and other healthcare professionals to create a safe and stimulating learning environment for patients. They adapt the curriculum and teaching methods to meet each student's individual needs, taking into account their medical conditions, cognitive and emotional abilities [3].

To be an effective hospital educator, it is important to have a solid understanding of pedagogical principles and practices, as well as a thorough understanding of medical conditions that can affect student learning and development. In addition, hospital educators must be able to

work in a team, have excellent communication skills and be able to handle emotionally challenging situations.

Hospital Pedagogy has a significant impact on students' lives. Studies show that continuing education during medical treatment can help reduce patients' stress and anxiety, improve their emotional well-being, and increase their chances of recovery. In addition, Hospital Pedagogy can help minimize the impact of hospitalization on students' educational trajectory, helping them to keep up with their studies and transition back to regular school when they are ready. Hospital Pedagogy also plays an important role in promoting social inclusion and equality. By ensuring that all students, regardless of their health condition, have access to quality education, hospital pedagogues help create a fairer and more inclusive society.

Despite its many contributions, Hospital Pedagogy faces several challenges. These include lack of institutional recognition and support, lack of resources and adequate training, and the difficulty of effectively integrating education and health care. However, with the commitment and dedication of hospital educators, and with the support of inclusive policies and practices, Hospital Pedagogy has the potential to transform the lives of many students [4].

In conclusion, Hospital Pedagogy is a vital area of pedagogy that plays a crucial role in promoting the right to education for all students, regardless of their health condition. To be a successful hospital educator, it is important to have a solid understanding of pedagogical principles and practices, a thorough understanding of medical conditions that can affect student learning and development, and the ability to work in teams and handle emotionally challenging situations. Despite the challenges, Hospital Pedagogy has the potential to make a significant difference in the lives of students and society in general.

REFERENCES

1. “Gematologiya, onkologiya, klinik immunologiya, boshqa statsionar va uzoq muddatli ambulator davolanishda bo‘lgan bolalarga ta’lim va tarbiya berish tizimini yanada kengaytirish chora-tadbirlari to‘g‘risida” O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasining 29.03.2023 yildagi 134-son qarori.
2. Pedro Anastácio de Oliveira, Gustavo Henrique dos Santos, Diogenes José Gusmão Coutinho PEDAGOGY IN HOSPITAL SETTING
3. PEDAGOGIA EM AMBIENTE HOSPITALAR doi.org/10.51891/rease.v9i3.8749.
4. Интервью С.В. Шариков «Для длительно болеющих детей учеба – единственная форма коммуникации» (рус.) (2017).
5. Kapelaki, U es mtsai (2012). A Novel Idea for an Organized Hospital/School Program for Children with Malignances: Issues in Implementation. *Pediatric Hematology and Oncology*, 20, 79-87.